

Principles of Sustainable Development and Education

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Abstract:

The article discusses the features of the implementation of the ideas and principles of education for sustainable development into the national education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, for training and retraining courses of managerial and teaching staff of higher and specialized secondary and vocational education. Analyzes the process of transformation of the national education system in the interests of sustainable development, is substantiated the role of education and need for developing comprehensive measures of development of education in sustainable development model.

Keywords: Education for Sustainable Development, principles of Sustainable development, Sustainable development-transformation, communication barriers.

Introduction. Taking into account the increasing uncertainty of political and economic development of the world community, strengthening the potential of various risks and threats, the task of realizing national sustainable development goals becomes especially urgent.

In modern conditions, mankind has faced the urgent need to develop and introduce into public life the concept of reasonable social behavior and development.

Among possible scenarios of society improvement the concept of sustainable development takes a special place. To face these challenges, the most effective tool that society has today is education.

Education for sustainable development is an emerging concept based on: universality and continuity of education; interdisciplinary approach; teacher-student interaction, discussion, learning through experience and creativity; combining education with upbringing; integration of the achievements of all modern branches of knowledge to create models of ecologically sustainable development of

societies.

1. Origin of the term "sustainable development" (SD) The term "sustainable development" itself appeared more than 20 years ago, when the UN World Commission on Environment and Development published the report of Norwegian Prime Minister and prominent figure of the social-democratic movement Gro Harland Brundtland "Our Common Future" (19-7). It raised for the first time the question of the need to find a new model of civilization and introduced the term sustainable development (SD), indicating a type of development that meets the vital needs of the population without compromising the future. The official campaign to combine the idea of sustainable development with the education and training system was initiated by UNESCO in the early 1990s. [1]

If we consider the implementation of education for sustainable development on the examples of developed countries, we can observe in the evaluation of the status of American ESD (PCSD), a special role is played by environmental education. The base of environmental education has spread in both formal and non-formal educational contexts, and environmental education has reached a degree of dominant acceptance. Many educators involved in ESD-related projects in the United States identify their work with environmental education. [2]

PCSD clearly articulates the idea of education for sustainability, stating, "Education for sustainability is a lifelong learning process that leads to an informed and engagement of a population with creative problem-solving skills, scientific and social literacy, to engage in responsible individual and collaborative action to create an environmentally, economically prosperous, and equitable society for present and future generations." France and Great Britain are trying to implement a balanced, thoughtful and consistent policy in the field of education on the principles of sustainable development. In June 2003, the French government approved the National Strategy for Sustainable Development, a project whose key concepts are solidarity and responsibility in the concrete implementation of the concept of sustainable development. In 2004, a new law on environmental education came into force, introducing the concept of sustainable development into official school programs. In college, the program touches almost all academic disciplines: history, geography, technology, exact sciences, civic education, sports, since all these subjects carry elements that allow to understand and reveal the main problems of the field of the concept of sustainable development. [3]

Education in SD is a dynamic component that includes all aspects of awareness of the state of nature and society, orienting towards building skills, vision and reinforcing values that will enable people of all ages to commit to creating a secure future.

The ideas of ESD are not yet well known even in the educational community of the country, which seriously hinders the process of implementation. The problem is slow integration of SD into sectoral and general courses, poor interaction between secondary and higher education, lack of motivation of teachers, university professors, civil servants and education authorities. There is a lack of real practice of ESD policy management and implementation in educational institutions. There is a lack of methodological materials, no practice of "operational access" to data in national languages via the Internet, adaptation to local cultural, historical, economic conditions, and lack of quality control in accordance with national standards. Training and retraining of personnel is still insufficient, the principles underlying education for sustainability are related to lifelong learning, practical experience-based learning, community-based learning, technology, family ownership, and personal responsibility." [4]

There are many examples of achievements in ESD and education in general in our country. In Uzbekistan, the role of higher education in ESD remains the leading one. And therefore it is important that the basics of SD are foreseen and included in the training and retraining of all specialists. Retraining of decision-makers and teachers for ESD should be carried out systematically

in all relevant institutions. And of course, in parallel with the development of theory and teaching methods, special attention will be needed to introduce "sustainable lifestyles" in practice, in the management of educational institutions at all levels.

Currently, the Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan on ESD is being implemented in the systems of formal (based on state educational standards) and non-formal (based on extracurricular, optional and additional classes) education, on the basis of ESD action plans

To date, due to the consistent implementation of the provisions of the above-mentioned laws, the National model of personnel training based on the principle of "individual - state and society - continuous education - science - production" has been formed in the republic.

There is no doubt that the inclusion of ideas and principles of sustainable development (SD) in education, including in the system of secondary specialized professional and higher education, is an absolute necessity to ensure sustainable development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. There are many ways to incorporate SD ideas directly into education, and this is partially realized, probably, in most educational institutions, however, such inclusions are not systematic. Such inclusions are not systematic, do not have a unified methodology that corresponds to the formed SD strategies, so they do not have a proper effect.

For example, many educational institutions hold campaigns to collect waste paper, scrap metal, plastic waste, organize "khashars" on landscaping and beautification, etc., aimed at educating young people to strive for cleanliness and order, to understand the role and complexity of work related to garbage collection. It is safe to assume that not all educational institutions, where such actions are held, the purpose is environmental education, often they are positioned as a way to earn money and fulfill the tasks of higher authorities. In this case, the environmental educational function of the events is almost completely lost. It is advisable that such initiatives should be accompanied by environmental actions, projects, contests and should be included in the work plans of each head and teaching staff of educational institutions of compulsory and higher education.

2. Ideas and principles of Sustainable Development in the system of personnel training and retraining.

Within the framework of a new educational model adapted to the goals of sustainable development, students should develop the ability to act in the context of a rapidly changing and poorly predictable future. In addition, such education should develop skills to anticipate the consequences of decisions, including possible consequences in the area of sustainability of environmental and socio-economic systems.

Despite the anti-crisis measures taken in different countries within the framework of national educational systems, the main problem of education - its orientation on the past - still exists. Special attention needs to be paid to initial training and retraining of educators and to creating opportunities for educators to share their experiences among teachers involved in the innovative process of becoming ESD educators. The innovation focus is strengthened when it is closely linked to relevant findings in the theory and practice of SD. Learning the basics of ESD depends on the content, quality and availability of teaching and learning materials on SD issues.

Include the concepts of development and environmental protection in all curricula with an analysis of the reasons causing the main problems; special attention should be paid to the training of future leaders.

Let us take into account the specificity of educational courses of advanced training and retraining (in the model of sustainable development) of the system of secondary and vocational education. Their goal should be the formation of students, managers and teachers of academic lyceums and colleges to teach students intellectual, personal, behavioral qualities, knowledge, skills, and abilities that allow an individual to adapt in a rapidly changing socio-natural environment. To achieve the

individual's general and professional competence, diplomacy, communication skills. It is also important to achieve the correspondence of psychological age of a person - to the calendar age, from the side of different periodizations. On the side of environmental education, it is important to make students understand how to behave in order not to harm the environment and why it is so important.

Let us concretize the ideas and principles of sustainable development to the professional development courses for managers and teaching staff of the system of secondary and vocational education in the form of a number of recommendations of SD-transformations of the educational process:

1. Education for Sustainable Development at advanced training and retraining courses can be realized in the form of introducing special courses on "sustainable development" within the framework of elective modules taken into account in the curricula. The course will allow to theoretically form the ecological culture of listeners.
2. Practice is the most important part, because it is not so much environmental knowledge that is important, but the formation of environmental behavior. Therefore, the programs of field trips, as well as excursions outside school hours should be supplemented with algorithms of actions to protect the environment, which helps students to acquire skills in teaching environmental behavior and the correct organization of environmental actions.
3. The principles of Sustainable Development should also be introduced in other modules (since the principles of SD are interdisciplinary): somewhere in the form of moral principles and environmental responsibility (e.g., in the module "Art of Leadership and Culture of Communication in Management"), somewhere in the form of theories and hypotheses ("Basic normative and legal documents of the SPSS system"), etc., and somewhere in the form of theories and hypotheses ("Basic normative and legal documents of the SPSS system").

It should be noted that it is academic lyceums and vocational colleges that are the ideal platform for informing. While maintaining the traditional emphasis on teaching individual subjects, opportunities for multilateral and interdisciplinary analysis of real-life situations should be supported to the maximum extent possible.

But the role of ecological knowledge must not be overemphasized, nor must there be a contradiction between suggested behaviors and real life. After all, environmental education by itself does not have a proper effect. An important reason for the low effectiveness of environmental education is the insufficient level of integration of environmental issues with social, cultural, economic and other issues. Thus, it is imperative to rely not only on the environmental component of Sustainable Development, but also to achieve integrity and ensure that students understand global processes and cause-and-effect relationships. Therefore, in addition to the environmental component of education, it is very important to create a system of socialization of students for sustainable development.

However, one should be careful here: if, for example, a teacher of general or specialized disciplines, integrating his subject with the model of Sustainable Development, intimidates students with global problems, he will create an image of a doomed Earth, while reorienting the education process to SD, it is necessary to create an image of a "sustainable" Earth. Consequently, when drawing up educational programs and methods, it is important to consider all such nuances at a competent level, before their implementation in the educational process and at advanced training and retraining courses for managers and teachers of secondary and vocational education. [5]

It is also necessary to reflect the strategic objectives of ESD in priority state programs and improve the quality of all levels of education by expanding access to different forms of education, increasing the professional competence of scientific and pedagogical staff and graduates of educational institutions. It is important to develop and implement educational programs based on problem-oriented interactive teaching methods, including ICT technologies and stimulating scientific activity

and ESD in the field of new technologies development.

ESD strategy implies reorientation of the main focus of teaching from knowledge provision to problem solving and search for possible solutions.[6].

3. Overcoming communication barriers in the concept of education for sustainable development.

In the concept of education for sustainable development, especially in the field of advanced training and retraining, great attention should be paid to overcoming communication barriers, because the learning process requires ideal communication between the teacher and the listener.[5].

As our experience shows, at least three communication barriers can be distinguished:

- ✓ The influence of the Pyramid of Needs (A. Maslow);
- ✓ The peculiarities of the age of the listeners;
- ✓ Complexity of the studied module.

Let's dwell more on the first communication barrier. Psychologist Abraham Maslow proposed the following classification of human needs:

1. Needs physiological (hunger, thirst, sex drive, life, etc.);
2. Safety needs (to feel protected, to get rid of fear and failure, aggressiveness, etc.);
3. Needs for belonging and love (belonging to a community, being close to people, being recognized and accepted by them, etc.);
4. Needs of respect, esteem (competence, achievement of success, authority, approval, recognition, etc.);
5. Cognitive needs (to know, to be able, to understand, to explore);
6. Aesthetic needs (harmony, symmetry, order, beauty, comfort, etc.);
7. Self-actualization needs (realization of one's goals, abilities, development of one's own personality).

According to this concept, it is difficult for a person to get a higher level need if lower level needs are not realized. Let's pay attention to the fifth point of the classification - these are cognitive needs - what it is necessary to cause in the student. But, according to A. Maslow, without the realization of the previous needs (Physiological, Safety, Belonging and love, Respect), the student will not want to learn, because he/she will not have a need for it (to know, to be able, to understand and to explore). Education for sustainable development is able to ensure the realization of the whole pyramid of needs in educational institutions.

Thus, for the realization of the first group of needs, the attention of the teacher is important - it is necessary to regularly check the physical condition of the classroom and training workshops. Unfortunately, many managers and teachers do not pay attention to ensuring proper conditions (cleanliness, heat, ventilation, etc.), as a result of which all the attention of students remains at the level of their dominant need at the moment, and the need for learning does not arise. Quality and varied nutrition, availability of an equipped medical room, creative and entertainment center, sports and gym are also important.

The second group of needs is solved both technically (modern security, video surveillance, pass system, turnstile) and psychologically (psychologist's work with the team, detection of risks, conflicts and their solution).

The third group of needs is the need for belonging and love, the desire to have a shared experience. Group types of classes, game lessons will help in this. In this case, the teacher should not be

alienated from the group of students - be a part of it.

The fourth group of needs is the needs of respect (and self-esteem). For the teacher it means - to praise for achievements, not to manipulate, not to insult. The realization of the third and fourth groups of needs depends entirely on the personal and professional qualities of teachers.

In a "sustainable" education system, the last two groups of needs are also satisfied: aesthetic needs (there are many plants on the territory of educational institutions, arbors for recreation, gardens, flower beds, new furniture, curtains, paintings, sculptures, upholstered furniture in the building; landscaping is one of the most important tasks of sustainable development) and the need for self-actualization - a student wants to realize his/her goals and abilities (experienced psychologists, teachers, masters of industrial training help him/her with this).

Ideally, after satisfying the first 4 groups of needs, the academic group will have a cognitive need: students want to acquire new knowledge, skills, abilities, want to understand new material. Gradually, on the basis of cognitive need, stable cognitive interests are formed. But it is not enough to cause this need, it must be satisfied. For this purpose, again, of great importance are courses of professional development and retraining of managers and teachers with a sustainable way of life and able to pass such an image to students, that is, changing for the better themselves and bringing up a harmoniously developed generation. And then, after graduating from an educational institution, a graduate of secondary specialized education will have a full understanding of the world around him, have a certain profession and make an adequate choice of his future place of work and, in fact, choose a suitable higher education institution.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the experience of Western countries in the process of developing a model of modernization of the educational system, education for sustainable development should be based on the application of new approaches and methods that absorbed all the positive things that gave the traditional system of education, but built on a different methodological basis, allowing to fully use the capabilities of information technology in combination with the traditions, culture and experience of local communities.

In the system of professional development and retraining of secondary and vocational education staff in order to develop education for sustainable development, there is challenging work to be done to ensure that leaders and educators acquire the skills to teach students who are able to make intergenerational connections (in terms of SD), to recognize the impact (be able to predict the consequences) of our actions on future generations, to understand how society functions and how it interacts with the environment, to respect the environment, to respect the rights of students, and to be able to understand the impact of our actions on future generations. Relate their personal interests to the interests of society and nature. Most importantly, to see the world as a unified system of interacting parts and to understand how some processes affect others.

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